

OPERATING CONDITIONS OF TRANSPORT VEHICLES

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Abstract: This article discusses the road conditions necessary for the operation of vehicles.

Key words: Car, road, maximum speed, carrying capacity, pavement, highways, intersections, safety, passenger, passenger car, operation.

There should be good roads for automobile transport. Roads must ensure continuous, safe and economical operation of vehicles at maximum speed. The increasing number of heavy-duty vehicles and multi-seater buses requires the rapid development of highways with improved surface [1]. In the country's economic and social development plans, great importance is attached to the expansion of hard-surfaced and improved road networks. Along with the construction of improved roads, it is necessary to expand road networks of local importance. Such road junctions are of great importance in expanding the exchange of goods, increasing agricultural production and the level of cultural life of the population [2].

In order to prevent cars and roads from being damaged quickly, it is necessary to produce cars that take into account road conditions, and in the construction of highways, it is necessary to take into account modern high-speed cars. Because such roads provide the least road resistance and also ensure traffic safety. Highways and urban roads are of great importance in the organization of passenger transportation by road transport [3]. Traffic safety, ease of passenger traffic, and consequently the productivity of drivers and other employees are closely related to the level of improvement and equipment of such roads. Labor productivity in motor transport enterprises largely depends on road conditions and its condition. Road conditions should be carefully studied before opening any new bus route and organizing the transportation of passengers by car taxis. The regulations for the operation of vehicles on the route are determined according to the road conditions [4]. In order to prevent vehicle accidents, the operational service of motor transport enterprises and road workers should

regularly study the road conditions. Employees of the operational service of passenger transport enterprises should be well aware of the requirements for roads. Highways and urban roads are a complex of engineering structures, which must ensure fast movement of vehicles and traffic safety. The construction of roads and the composition of engineering structures are inextricably linked with the speed and speed of movement set for them, as well as local natural climatic conditions. Road signs, signals and other traffic regulation equipment are an integral part of roads [5].

Public highways connect regions, cities, district centers, railway stations, airports, Amudarya wharves and other places in our country. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, such roads are owned by the state concern "Uzavtoyol". In addition to public highways, there are also roads belonging to various departments, which serve to connect objects within industrial enterprises, construction, agriculture (water) and other enterprises. There are state and technical classifications for describing roads. According to the state classification, highways are divided into:

- a) roads of national significance. They unite the centers of neighboring countries, regional centers of our republic, large industrial and cultural centers. Such roads include roads leading to large resorts;
- b) roads of regional significance. Such roads serve to connect district centers with each other and with regional centers or highways of national importance, major railway stations, airports, wharves;
- c) roads of local significance. Such roads include all roads of district importance and within farms [1].

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